

PROCESS AND TRIBOLOGICAL BEHAVIOR OF 6061 AL/GR._(P) COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY: The present study, the composite of 6061 Al alloy castings which contained graphite particles which are $6\mu\text{m}$ of an average particle size with 2,4,6 wt% has been produced successfully by ourselves. The wettability between the graphite particles and the 6061 Al alloy matrix is improved by coated copper on the graphite particles. The composites which have cast with the smaller graphite particles are so superior than the composites which have cast with the larger graphite particles in tensile property. The fractograph of 6061 Al alloy is a shear cleavage style, the fractograph of composites becomes the cup and cone without obvious necking. The weight loss decreases with the increasing of graphite particle contents and wear speed. The worn surfaces coarse grooves morphology, however, the number of coarse grooves of 6061 Al alloy is more than 6061 Al alloy-graphite particles composites after wear test. Moreover, the bands between the coarse grooves have been found. The band width of 6061 Al alloy-graphite particles composite is wider than 6061 Al alloy.

KEYWORDS: composites, yield stress, tensile stress, hardness, graphite particles, tribology, coated copper, cementation process fractograph, wear rate, seizure,

INTRODUCTION

About 40 % of the power loss in engine system is attributed to the adverse effects of friction in reciprocating engine components[1]. In order to improve the efficient of engine and enable fuel economics to be gained in transport engineering application, the fabrication of the engine system will be through weight and wear rate reduction and lubricating condition addition between the contact objects[2,3]. Aluminium alloys provide designers and engineers with a group of materials with valuable properties which include: excellent corrosion resistance; high specific strength; high electrical and thermal conductivities[2,4], however, it also has a weakness in wear resistance[2]. During the past 15 years, the researchers who were Rohatgi et al.[2,5,6] had worked on the development in aluminium alloy-graphite particles composites. Under optimum conditions, the aluminium-graphite composite becomes self-lubricating because of the transfer of the graphite particles embedded into the tribosurfaces and its formation into a thin film which prevents direct contact between the worn surfaces. The coefficient of friction; contact temperature rise and wear rate could be reduced .

According to the investigative reports[5-17] of tribology in aluminium alloy-graphite particles composites by Rohatgi et al., the tribological behaviors would be affected by some parameters

which include: the shape and containing of graphite particles, the bonding strength between the graphite particles and aluminium alloy, the processes of fabrication and the sliding wear conditions. According to Gibson et al.[2,5], a reduction in efficient of friction, wear rate and contact temperature rise, due to add the graphite particles at low addition levels about 2wt%. However, at high addition levels as 8wt%, the mechanical properties have been reduced significantly. The coefficient of friction in composites containing granular graphite is lower than composites which contain flake graphite as reported by Liu et al.[16]. Prasad et al. have studied that if the bonding between particle and matrix is poor, the interface as equivalent to preexisting cracks. According to Rohatgi et al.[18,19], graphite particles can be coated Cu or Ni which increased the wettability and decreased the porosity between the graphite and matrix in composites. Prasad et al[7]. has reported that composites have been manufactured by powder metallurgy process, however, it has reverse effect in tribological properties. This anomalous behavior was attributed to increased porosity in the composites. Gibson et al. has manufactured the composites which were added suitable amounts of graphite particles by compocasting process[2], due to the dry sliding wear test, found to possess superior dry wear properties over the matrix alloy. The cluster of graphite particles was investing by Prasad[7] who concluded that crack nucleation due to cluster by graphite particles, such that could be reveal tribological behavior. The applied pressure could be increased without seizure when the 6061 Al alloy added graphite particles as reported by Prasad et al.[6]. As the sliding velocity increases, the wear rate was decreased by Rohatgi et al.[20] The wear rate was increased as increasing sliding distances as reported by Gibson et al.[2] In fully or partially lubricated conditions of 6061 Al alloy matrix with SAE30 oil on a pin-on-disc wear test apparatus, the wear speed and the applied pressure range could be increased without seizure. However, the P-V limits of the aluminium-graphite particles composites are higher than the aluminium alloy matrix by Das et al.[6]

In this paper, the process of 6061 Al alloy castings contain graphite particles which are $6\ \mu\text{m}$ of an average particle size with 2,4,6 wt% have been investigated. Moreover, we also explore the effect of 6061Al alloy add $6\ \mu\text{m}$ graphite particles in tensile stress, hardness and tribological properties.

EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

Materials Preparation

The chemical composites of the 6061 aluminium alloy are 0.532%Si-0.833%Mg-0.035%Mn-0.207%Cu-0.149%Fe-0.0165%Ti-0.103%Cr. The lubricant phases used in this work are a graphite particle with a mean size of $6\ \mu\text{m}$. Composites containing up to 6wt% graphite particles were prepared by a prior technique, which involved the steps of mixing and degassing, where the graphite particles were coated copper by cementation process prior to add 6061 molten alloy, the coated copper procedure shows as Fig.1 and has been reported elsewhere[19] . Specimens for the hardness, tensile and wear tests were cut and machinery from these composites and T6 treatment ($532\ ^\circ\text{C}$ 2hr, $160\ ^\circ\text{C}$ 18hr).

Mechanical Test

The hardness tests were performed by using B-Scale Rocker's hardness apparatus (load time fully plastic deformation is 47 sec); tensile tests were performed by using Instron tensile apparatus with 5mm/min cross head speed.

Wear Test

The wear test, which were of the pin-on-disc type. Before the wear tests, each specimen was ground up to grade 1200 abrasive paper, making sure that the wear surface completely contacted the surface of the disc (HRC 62 ± 2). Wear tests were carried out under dry conditions by sliding the specimen under applied constant load up to 29.4N and constant sliding velocity up to 0.8m/sec. The weight losses were calculated from the difference in weight of the specimens measured before and after the test to the nearest 0.1mg using an analytical balance. For all tests were performed at room temperature (27°C, relative humidity 75%), for each test data, at least six runs were performed. Microstructural observations were carried out using an optical microscope (OM) on the graphite particles distributed in the 6061 Al matrix.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Coated Copper by Cementation Process

Fig.1 shows the flow chart of graphite particles be coated copper. According to the paper [19,21], copper can be displaced from the copperbearing salts by Zn by the following cementation process.

The displaced copper from CuSO_4 in the nascent form has a positive charge for a period and the surface of suspended graphite particles in the solution is likely to have a negative charge as reported by [22]. Fig.2 shows the coated copper on the surface of graphite particles. According to Fig.2(b) and (c) of EDS and Mapping analysis respectively, the copper elements have been detected on the surface of graphite particles uniformly. According to the Fig.2, the surface of graphite particles was covered with uniform copper.

Dispersion of Copper Coated Graphite Particles in 6061 Al Alloy

Fig.3 shows the microstructures of the 6061 Al alloy and the composites with 2,4,6 wt% graphite particles. Fig.4 shows the magnification from Fig.3(d) by SEM. According to the Fig.4, 6 μm graphite particles have been added in the aluminium alloy. Moreover, the graphite particles have been dispersed in the aluminium alloy uniformly as shown in Fig.3. Consequently, according to the Fig.3 and 4, we have produced the composites of 6061 Al alloy-6 μm graphite particles composites successfully by our processing equipment and casting condition which were designed by ourselves in this experiment. However, we can't produce the composites which add 6 μm graphite particles without any coated copper in our processing route and the same casting condition. This is attributed to the graphite particles can't be wet with the aluminium molten and the density of graphite particle is less than the

aluminium molten, so that the graphite particles were floating up to the molten and can't uniform mixture with the aluminium molten.

Tensile Properties

The variations in mechanical properties with 6061 Al alloy and 6061Al/2,4,6 wt% graphite particles composites are shown in Table 1. The ultimate tensile stress and yield stress decreases with the increases in graphite particles contents were expected. For example, the ultimate tensile stress of the 6061 Al alloy is 26.3 kg/mm^2 and the composite which contains $6 \mu \text{ m}$ and 2 wt% graphite particles is 22.4 kg/mm^2 . There is a 14.8% reduction in ultimate tensile stress. According to the paper[23], the Al-12wt%Si with $40 \mu \text{ m}$ and 2wt% graphite particles composites, the tensile stress reduces from 207 MPa in the matrix to 164 MPa. There is a 20.7% reduction in tensile stress. This is attributed to the cracks of the larger graphite particles have been nucleated and created the stress concentration that could be reduced the fracture toughness easier than the smaller graphite particles. Moreover, the graphite particles are soft structure. Consequently, the composites which have cast with the smaller graphite particles are so superior than the composites which have cast with the larger graphite particles in tensile property. Moreover, the elongation and hardness of the composites have no obvious decrease with increase the graphite particles as shown in Table 1. Otherwise, the fractograph of tensile test specimens, the shear cleavage of the matrix alloy, the fractograph of composites were become cup and cone style but has no obvious necking with increased the graphite particles. This is attributed to the crack nucleation, propagation and linking up between the interface of graphite particles and Al alloy.

Tribological Behavior

Fig.5 shows that the weight loss versus graphite particles contents of 6061 Al alloy- $6 \mu \text{ m}$ graphite particles composites. The weight loss has obvious decrease with increasing the graphite particle contents. This is attributed to the high level addition of graphite particles can form the lubricating film to prevent the direct contact wear in the short time compared with the low addition in the same wear condition. Fig.6 shows that microstructures of worn surface. Fig.6(a) and (b) show the worn surface morphology of 6061 Al alloy and 6061 Al alloy-6wt% graphite particles composites before wear test respectively. According to the Fig.6(a) and (b), the surfaces are rough and with fine grooves. This is attributed to the each specimen who has been polished by grade 1200 abrasive paper, making sure that the wear surface completely contacted the surface of the disc. Fig.6(c) and (d) show the worn surface morphology of 6061 Al alloy and 6061 Al alloy-6wt% graphite particles composites after wear test. According to Fig.6(c) and (d), the surfaces reveal coarse grooves, however, the number of coarse grooves of 6061 Al alloy is more than 6061 Al alloy-6wt% graphite particles composites after wear test. Moreover, the bands between the coarse grooves have been found. The band width of 6061 Al alloy-6wt% graphite particles composite is wider than 6061 Al alloy matrix as shown in Fig.6(c) and (d). This is attributed to the mating surface of 6061 Al alloy has no lubricants, so that the seizure was happened seriously on the mating surface as shown in Fig.6(c). Moreover, the 6061 Al alloy-graphite particles composites becomes self-lubricating because of the transfer of the graphite particles embedded in its matrix to the tribosurfaces and its formation into a thin film which prevents direct contact and seizure between the mating surface. Fig.7 shows that wear weight loss versus wear speed. It shows that the weight loss decreases with increasing the wear speed and graphite particle content, especially in wear speed of 0.8m/s and graphite content of 6wt %, the wear loss

amounts of composites were less than others. Moreover, in the same graphite particle content and wear condition, the weight loss decreases with increasing the wear speed.

CONCLUSION

In this paper, the composite of 6061 Al alloy castings which contained graphite particles which are $6\ \mu\text{m}$ of an average particle size with 2,4,6 wt% has been produced successfully by ourselves. The wettability between the graphite particles and the 6061 Al alloy matrix is improved by coated copper by cementation process on the surface of graphite particles. Moreover, the graphite particles dispersed in the 6061 Al alloy matrix uniformly from the observation of the microstructure. In this paper, we also explore the effect of 6061 Al alloy add $6\ \mu\text{m}$ graphite particles in tensile stress, hardness and tribological properties as detailed below:

1. The elongation and hardness have no obvious reduction with increasing graphite particle contents.
2. The composites which have cast with the smaller graphite particles are so superior than the composites which have cast with the larger graphite particles in tensile property.
3. The fractograph of 6061 Al alloy is a shear cleavage style, when 6061 Al alloy adding the graphite particles the fractograph become the cup and cone with no obvious necking.
4. The weight loss decreases with increasing of graphite particles contents and wear speed.
5. The worn surfaces reveal coarse grooves morphology, the number of coarse grooves of 6061 Al alloy are more than 6061 Al alloy-graphite particles composites after wear test. Moreover, the bands between the coarse grooves have been found. The band width of 6061 Al alloy-graphite particles composite is wider than 6061 Al alloy.

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Fig.1: The flow chart of coated copper by cementation process on graphite particles

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig.2: (a)Scanning electron micrographs (b)DES (c)Mapping analysis of coated copper on graphite particle surface

Fig.3: Optical micrographs of 6 μ m graphite particles dispersed in 6061 Al alloy matrix (a)0wt%(b)2wt%(c)4wt%(d)6wt% (Magnification, 500X)

Fig. 4: Scanning electron micrograph of 6 μ m graphite particles dispersed in 6061 Al alloy (Magnification 5000X)

Table 1 Mechanical properties of 6061 Al alloy containing different percentage of 6 μ m graphite particles

property Gr. _(p) %	Yield stress (kg/mm ²)	Ultimate tensile stress (kg/mm ²)	Elongation %	Hardness HRB
0wt%	20.4	26.3	9.46	60
2wt%	22.3	22.4	4.62	62
4wt%	18.9	18.9	2.98	58
6wt%	13.0	13.0	3.33	52

Fig.5: Wear weight loss of 6061 Al alloy- graphite particle composites as a function on graphite particle contents: sliding speed, 0.6m/s; sliding distance, 144m; applied pressure 0.69 MPa

Fig.6: Optical micrographs of worn surface of (a)matrix alloy and (b)6 wt% composite before wear test, (c)matrix alloy and (d)6 wt% composite after wear test: sliding speed 0.6m/s; sliding distance 144m; applied pressure 0.69 MPa (Magnification, 200X)

Fig.7: Wear weight loss of 6061 Al alloy-graphite composites as a function on wear speed: sliding distance, 144m; applied pressure 0.69 MPa